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The human brain in Language

There is a lot of interest nowadays among different researchers and linguists in the relation between the development of the language and evolution of the language and human features that are regarding to language is in several ways but they also compare the language with the communication that it exists in other live beings and that are also those who see the onset of language ability as a qualitative leap the discontinuity view that are those on both sides of the discontinuity view, who believed that language is just as specific. In order to comprehend the process of language people have the past the present future.

For many years the language have changed in the past we used to have people with words and the choice of them were different than the ones in the present, where the communication is different since we use a wide variety of applications to communicate and that help us to express our feelings with only one click away. But if we continue at this pace, will there be any communication in the future? It has been suggested that the speech could not have developed in non-human primates because their vocal tracks where anatomically incapable of producing a large enough inventory of speech sounds. With this being said, we can say that the ability of a speaking mainly belongs to humans being those who are able to understand a message with only looking at the other person to see their facial expressions and interpret the tone of their voice and of words.

Also, there are hypotheses that say the language is linked to the evolution and also the development of the speech when it comes to production and perception. This is mainly related to the evolution does in the brain and the nervous system the order to obtain more complexity. This view also implies that language of our human ancestors of millions of years ago might have been syntactically and phonology simpler than any other language that we know it today and with this staying there simpler is not that is easy; it is just that the word that existed back then and the language and the use of sounds were less than the ones that we have now.

Furthermore, another important event that happened in the evolution of the human to get to the facility of producing different sounds was their development of a vocal tract capable of producing the different sounds of human language as well as the mechanism for perceiving and distinguishing them. In the other hand we have birds and parrots in which this step is insufficient to explain the origin of the language these creatures have the ability to imitate human speech but not the ability to acquire the language nor understanding more complex ideas, therefore; they might have a possibility of imitating but not going to beyond than that part. In the other hand, we know of humans who are born deaf and learn sign language. The acquisition and

use of the language and they can communicate although their vocal tract is not like the other ones or simply because they do not have the ability to listen but the communication in their brain is there, with or without sounds or words. Then also we have that lateralization evidence from brain damaged, it shows that the brain is neurologically equipped to learn language rather than speech.

The linguist Noam Chomsky expresses this View:

It could be that when the brain reached a certain level of complexity it simply automatically had certain property because that's what happens when you pack 10 neurons into something the size of a basketball.

Other languages however, linguists say that the most accurate theory for language with brain is the natural selection development of what is called the language instinct for instance all the evidence suggests that is the precise wiring of the brains microcircuits that makes language happen, the combination of all its components makes this happen.

Finally, language most likely to evolve with the human species boss and bleed in his stages and also possibly in one giant leap the different researchers, linguists and evolutionary biologists and even neurologists support these few and the view that from the outset the human animal was genetically equipped to learn language that is up the evolutionary development of the brain provide some evidence for physiological and anatomic preconditions for language development.

Reference:

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